

Employability Skills on Arts and Science College Students

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 2

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.112

Citation:
Kavitha, A., and
C. Anusuya.
“Employability Skills
on Arts and Science
College Students.”
*Shanlax Internatioanl
Journal of Management*,
vol. 6, no. S2, 2019,
pp. 1–9.

DOI:
[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2591068](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2591068)

Dr.A.Kavitha, M.Com., M.B.A., M.Phil., Ph.D.,

*Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration
Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal College, Sivakasi*

C.Anusuya

*Ph.D. Research Scholar, PG and Research Department of Commerce
Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal College, Sivakasi*

Abstract

India attracts the attention of the world for its abundance of human capital, which is youthful in comparison with other countries. The massive growth of this demographic dividend needs mammoth efforts in the Indian history by exhibiting their dexterity in Science and Arts. There are highly educated youth in the unemployment queue - In the process of economic development, the major players are the graduates in the development of any nation. The term ‘employability’ has been used for many years by employers, Governments and researchers in the context of nation’s development. The stake holders must have the two wings of contextualization and conceptualization to have the wings of fire as quoted by our former President (Late) Dr. A. P. J. Abdul Kalam to visualize India to become the developed nation by 2020. Employability skills are the very basic skills necessary for acquiring, sustaining and pursuing the goals. The skills which are expected by the employers are broadly classified into five heads. The factors influencing the employability skills and the sources of acquiring the employability skills would be incomplete if the strategies to impart the employability skills are not considered. The mismatch between the skills possessed by the graduates and the skills expected by the employers could be addressed as the ‘skill gap’. ‘Indian youth to be kept under the shelter of the mighty wings of the Government policy’. Only 33.95% were found employable, same can be interpreted that 2/3 of the skill pool is not fit to have a job. ‘Employability skills’ are those skills essential for receiving, keeping and being successful in a job. The number of graduates crowned by a university is not the indication of the quality of education, and then the number of crowns and gowns on the convocation day will be the number of enrollment in the job market.

Keywords: Employability skill, Arts and Science, Skill gap, job market etc.,

Introduction

India attracts the attention of the world for its abundance of human capital, which is youthful in comparison with other countries. This youth potential if directed towards the right path would enable one to attain the status of developed nation in the near future. Subsequently, monitoring and moulding this human capital would be the source of blessing to the nation, to the organization, to the family and to one’s self.

The following three dimensional issues of the country’s youth population would involuntarily invite the suggestions from the policy makers and stakeholders to prevent its ineffective way of operation.

- India is expected to become the most populous nation by 2030 reaching 1.46 bn.
- It will also have one of the youngest populations in the world by 2030, with a median age of 32 years, as compared with other countries.
- Industry and service sectors are expected to contribute 92% of India's GDP by 2030 and require a net / gross incremental workforce of 145 m / 250 m respectively. (British Council Report 2015).

The aforesaid issues need the structural design to be framed by the stakeholders, which comprise the policy makers, the educational institutions, the parents, obviously last but not the least, the students. Participation Strategy (2012-2015) envisages that "every young person should have an individualised learning plan that provides a personalised, flexible route map to guide their progression journey from school". To have the knowledge based economy, the human resource, especially the youth of the nation, have to stand in the fore front in order to fill the gap by presenting themselves as a competent and vibrant force. The role of the interested parties in grooming the young minds to uphold the nation in its endeavors cannot be left unnoticed by the continual dripping in the stream of measures undertaken, which needs to be addressed at the earliest.

The Prevalent Competency of the Youth

The way forward for youth competency is skillfulness or work readiness. The massive growth of this demographic dividend needs mammoth efforts in the Indian history by exhibiting their dexterity in Science and Arts. The report presented by Learners First (2012) proudly pronounces that "India enjoys a unique advantage not only to fulfill its internal demand of skill manpower, but also cater to the labor shortage in other countries". This reveals that our barn is filled with human talents both at the home and at the international front. The expectation of the employers have to match with the potentials of the youth, this is the juncture at which the stakeholders' momentum in enhancing the skills of the youth is looked-for. What matters most for the competence of the youth is creating knowledge. In this aspect, the Confederation of British Industry Report (CBI) 2011 - states that "the development of employability skills among young people at schools and colleges is not for new qualification, but to embed the skills in the curriculum, as the best institutions already do". The granular understanding of this, will take away the essence of its implementation to the maximum extent. As the students are aware of the skill enhancement, so their employment opportunities improve.

The Field is White, But the Laborers are Few

There are highly educated youth in the unemployment queue - In the process of economic development, the major players are the graduates in the development of any nation. It is quite amazing and astonishing to see the erudite in the list of unemployed and the nation builders in the massive crowd of unemployment because, the reason is none other than the employability skills. The society expects more from the educated youth; the educated youth expects employment from society. The employability skill strikes the equilibrium in the balance between the education and employment. Employability skill addresses itself as a lubricant for the vehicle used in the journey of hunting a job. Employability skills are generic in nature and are eagerly received by all industry types and job levels from the bottom level to the top most position. Unfortunately, these employability skills are considered to be the stumbling block for some young people due to their failure to equip themselves with the job readiness skills.

Fixing The Square Pegs Into the Square Holes

Employability manifests itself in various ways, for the technician it is the technology, for the marketing person it is the communication, for the senior executive it is the higher thinking skills. The motivating and positive effect is that the employability skills are teachable, in other words, these skills are learnable, one who accepts this statement will be motivated to the highest level of satisfaction or one who disdains this, would place the employability barrier in the path. The term ‘employability’ has been used for many years by employers, Governments and researchers in the context of nation’s development. One cannot give the tailor made answer to the questions encompassing the skills. The skill changes its nature according to the size and expectation of the industry it pertains, but the quality remains the same that is, what is expected of the person, must be possessed by him. The entire dream would come true; all the resources invested for the quality education would be utilized to the optimum level - if a single yardstick, simple measuring device is available. In the practical realm, one has to be with cool head and hot foot to pursue the skills, which he come across or to trace it out with the ceaseless effort in the light of the employer expectations and the current trends in the society.

The outcries of the people who are affected directly or sensitively is the most spoken and the least understood concept called ‘employability skills’, have to be proclaimed louder to be heard by the huge mass and to make it known to the stakeholders:

Ignorant parents - are worried as to why their son/daughter is not selected for the job

Innocent Youth - wonder as to how they could attain their dream job, Stereotyped

Educational Institutions - watch helplessly as their graduates are not able to fit in themselves in the job market

Visionary Management Institutes - seek for trainees who have the thirst and passion to pursue the training

Cosmopolitan Corporate sectors - look out for a person among the youth, who would fulfill the organizational plan,

Commercial banks- are wary as to the state of their funds, they lent for higher studies; Exploratory Researchers on this topic- await new factors.

These above mentioned queries can be fulfilled in a single capsule, called employability skills. At the same time, it cannot be considered as the tailor made solution for unemployment and underemployment. It needs 360 degree mentoring to dig out the hidden treasures (youth potential) in the land of India. Vivienne Stern, the Director of UK Higher Education International Unit of British Council report (2015) states that “India will soon have the largest tertiary education age population in the world and will be a vital source of the global graduate workforce as well as a major producer of future research talent”.

Contextualization and Conceptualization are the Parallel Tracks in Skill Hunt

The stake holders must have the two wings of contextualization and conceptualization to have the wings of fire as quoted by our former President (Late) Dr. A. P. J. Abdul Kalam to visualize India to become the developed nation by 2020. In tune with this saying the honourable President of India, Dr. Pranab Mukherjee while addressing the youth about the demographic dividend highlighted that out of the 723 universities, 35,000 colleges, 16 IITs, 30 NITs and a number of institutes of management in India, none of them find their place among the top class 200 universities of the world (Yahoo India News). This alerts the stakeholders of the education to utilize the vitality of the youth by enhancing the skill in par with the international standards.

The economic development of any nation, without equipping the youth with the required skills, will undoubtedly lose its charm in the progress of lifting up the nation.

So-called skills are the well knit set of actions to be taken by a young mind hunting for job before finishing the final semesters. In the current scenario, the exodus of the youth has started towards achieving the needed skills, understanding the passion, an unquenchable thirst of becoming someone (whom they have chosen as the role model or to become a multi skilled) to be understood by the stakeholders of the total educational scenario.

A new entrant into the job market must be familiar with the basic skills called 'generic skills' which travel across the nature and type of the industries. The person who is skillful on this basis is considered to be fittest of the survival. As everyone is aware, the basic skills comprise literacy, numerical accuracy and computing skills are expected to be acquired from the academic curricula.

Importance of Employability Skills

Employability skills - an armor to withstand the environmental changes

The concept of employability cannot be unpinned with a single connotation. Every student longs for it, every educational institution strives for it, and every employer waits for it. It is the educational institution and the employers' prerogative to decide on course curriculum. Employability skills are the very basic skills necessary for acquiring, sustaining and pursuing the goals. These are the skills, qualities and behavior that makes the employees to mingle with their peers and to get along with the job environment that encompasses them. While mentioning the importance of it, Brown P. Hesketh et al. (2003) comments that "the employability not only depends on whether one is able to fulfill the requirements of specific jobs, but also on how one stands relative to others within a hierarchy of job seekers".

The skills that are mostly expected by the employers

The skills which are expected by the employers are broadly classified in to the following five major headings:

Basic skills

- Literacy
- Numerical accuracy and
- Computing skills

In addition to the basic skills, there are other skills that are expected by the employers on the basis of the job requirements. In current job market scenario, the graduates who are equipped with the following skills, keep their employer happy and find greater job security.

Personal skills

These skills include

- Communication
- Technological
- Personality development
- Interpersonal relationship
- Capacity to learn
- Creativity
- Using numbers effectively
- Using language effectively
- Aesthetic skills and Personal appearance

High order thinking skills

- Intellectual
- Analytical
- Leadership
- Emotional
- Intelligence
- Stress Tolerance
- Resolving conflicts
- Decision making and Crisis management

Corporate sector skills

- Global awareness
- Understanding the business
- Capacity to learn
- Team work
- Understanding
- Self management and Resource management

Skills related to the community

- Moral values
- Sympathy and
- Empathy

The skill which serves as the basic necessity for employment. The researcher has shown the interest in finding out awareness of the students about the basic skills which paved the way for entry into the job, which are Communication skill, Computing skills (Computer knowledge) and Numerical Accuracy. The confidence of the students is the essential ingredient in the process of preparing the students to face the interview. Subsequently, this upholds the employee by providing the job security. In this research, the factors responsible for making the students to gain confidence to secure a job and reflect the same at the time of interview are measured. The confidence level of the students is measured as the interpersonal factors and the variables selected for measuring the confidence level are boldness to face the interview, communication skills, fear factors, body language and skill updating.

The parents' encouragement, guidance and advice for the child in the education perform the miracles in the career of their child, but in the practical realm it is the rare jewel found in most of the families. In this research, the parental role and the association of the parents with the academic aspects of their offspring is measured as the personal factors.

The academic qualities which provides the platform for the skill enhancement is measured as the academic factors in which the reputation of the institution, participation in seminars, conferences and intercollegiate competitions and skill updating are embedded as the variables. The employability skills, the whole armour to be put on by the students who has to withstand the environmental changes in the form of technology, culture and other social issues cannot be infused to the students by force, but one must have the heart and mind prepared to receive it and reap the benefits of that. In this research, the Students' willingness to learn the employability skills is measured by the technical term learning to learn.

Lack of employability skill is the reason for unemployment, at the same time, lack of awareness of employability skills is the outcome for lack of employability skills. Keeping the aforesaid issue, the research is conducted to find out the ways and means the student come across the employability

skills, because before sowing the seeds called employability skills there must be the sources to get informed about the skills.

The factors influencing the employability skills and the sources of acquiring the employability skills would be incomplete if the strategies to impart the employability skills are not considered. The aforesaid issues of employability skills are discussed and the same is analysed in the opinion of the students. The skills which are considered as the fine tuning elements in the career of the youth, needs careful attention by the stakeholders of education. The transition phase of imparting the skills needs the watchful efforts, because this is the stage, the hindrances like deterioration in quality, misconception, prolonging, unsuitable methods and the environmental pressures would intervene and change the real spirit of skill development. To support this in the words of Beutel Denise. A (2010) “teachers work with more diverse communities in times characterized by volatility, uncertainty and moral ambiguity. Societal, political, economic and cultural shifts have transformed the contexts in which teachers work”.

Skillfulness of the Skill Providers Outweighs the Obstacles

Unless and otherwise a person is filled with a particular caliber, transfusing the same to others is of difficulty. Brent Galloway (1998) insists on “the effective instruction, to empower students to access the knowledge they bring with them to the classroom to build new knowledge”. The author adds that “most people seem to learn best when: that which they already know is recognized, respected and built upon” here the teacher is portrayed as an enabler rather than the provider. The instructors must have the deeper knowledge tested with the practical implications to train others. To support this view in the words of Safaa Mohammad (2012) “language instructors are recommended to focus on building their students’ selfconfidence through creating a supportive, classroom environment that encourages them to speak and participate in oral activities without fear. The author also suggests that “they can help learners recognize their fears and help them learn to deal with them. They can support positive thinking and fight negative views and beliefs. During oral activities, they should maintain a relaxed and humorous atmosphere; design interesting activities, give more time and opportunities and concentrate on the positive”.

“The skillfulness of the parents, the least knowledge if not the proficiency counts a lot in the journey of the career building task, which includes the academic and the pedagogical strategies of the schools” Joanne Steinmann et al. (2000-2008). Here the authors stress on the importance of the parental role in stepping out the expected way to evince sharp interest in their child’s career. The vivid understanding regarding the skill competency of the youth is expected on the part of the policy makers. The source of all blessed efforts proceeds only out of the policy making criteria though it differs vertically on the basis of hierarchy and horizontally on the basis of the region it penetrates. The stronger it is emphasized, more powerful the end result is, so the proclamation of the importance of the skill building capacity as a nation’s task must be underpinned with the benefits, consequential effects on the nation’s welfare and the personal achievements of the institutions through rewards both in the positive and negative way. One of the most important constraints for the effective implementation of the employability skills is the lack of research in this area to dig out the feasibility measures according the nature of the institutions, and the nature of the academic discipline. The suggestion offered by Kevin Lowden et al. (2011) is “the Government should consider the ways of reflecting and promoting the employability skills and attributes in funding mechanisms such as the Research Excellence Framework”. The Government and the various apex bodies regulating the education to ensure the quality of education, the right amount of funds at the right time, for the right mass adds the essence. The role of the employer cannot be curtailed with the limit of providing the employment offer, invites the step ahead to have the participative or hands on approach with the educational institutions. “The employer engagement requires an alignment

between the strategic, practical and personal needs and aspirations of employers, providers and learners, says Richard Bolden et al. (2008)". Earlier the best, the employers who are vibrant in their goals, by the influence of the globalization, liberalization and privatization, to take the measures in proclaiming their corporate goals in the premises of the educations to be understood by the institutions, the teachers and the students.

The peer group influence in the adolescent age of a person imposes a major impact in crafting the career path can be utilized in a psychological phenomenon for the skill enhancement of the students. The numerous research works in this area has approved that the formal method (other sources of employability skills) of approach is fallen short of its effectiveness in the formative years, when the peer group influence has played a major role in disseminating the information about the employment and the expectation of the employers.

The Skill Gap Widens the Gap of Nation's Development

The students, who appear for the interview on being rejected, complain and groan for not being selected. On the other side, the employers who conducted the interview are disappointed as candidates do not possess the employability skills as desired. The mismatch between the skills possessed by the graduates and the skills expected by the employers could be addressed as the 'skill gap'. The skill gap is due to various reasons like lack of communication and other soft skill, uncommitted way of imparting the academic knowledge which is the main source of developing the skills, not updating the curriculum with the recent trends in the job market, unpreparedness of the students to learn the needed skill, unmindful attitude of the parents are taken as the important ingredients and by keeping the above mentioned reasons of skill gap.

A student who has come across all the refining process during the graduation period and qualified as a graduate is considered to be unqualified by the interview panel. The aforesaid incident is not a strange thing that happens for one in thousands, which calls for careful planning on the part of the policy makers. "Employability skills are not a substitute for specific knowledge and technical skills, they make the difference between being good at a subject and being good at doing a job" as per the report of United Kingdom Commission on Employability skills (UKCES 2009). A one sided tremendous victory on the day of convocation, the student undergoes the mental agony of being rejected by the employer, which is the serious cause to be dealt by policy makers and the stakeholders of the education. The contextual aspect of this failure, rejection, non-selection by the employer must be analyzed by considering the various aspects of the education of the students and the expectation of the employer and thereby one could find out the gap between these two paradigms and the same is uttered by the society as the 'skill gap' and which is exposed in this research as the research gap.

Institution Industry Partnership (IIP)

In order to have the realistic approach of learning, the students must enter into the chambers of the organization or the employers must visit the campus of the educational institutions. This hand on approach will fetch the needed results of narrowing down the 'skill gap'. The Educational institutions must take up the initiative in bridging the gap by having the bridge course with the concerned people, where the employers, teachers and the students are the partakers.

Policy to Govern the Indian Youth

'Indian youth to be kept under the shelter of the mighty wings of the Government policy'. It is the time for India to protect the talents of the future work force from its quality deterioration. The ultimate authority vested in the hands of the policy makers, to safeguard the skills of the youth from being undeveloped and underdeveloped.

The skilled graduates waiting to be procured as hotcakes not to be left as half baked, where the utility is lost and the resources invested for the education will add up the cost to the Government budget. The Government must take measures in tune with the requirement of the employers of home country as well from the international labour market. According to India Skills Report (2015) “campaigns like Make in India that aim at turning the country into a global manufacturing hub and increase the per capita income by creating jobs for over 10 million people are such initiatives to have the move of Indian economy from a services-driven growth model to a labour-intensive manufacturing-driven growth, which is much more sustainable”.

Employability Skills for Arts and Science College Students in Tamil Nadu

The India Skills Report (2014) presented the study conducted by Wheelbox Employability Skill Test (WEST) “an instrument to gauge the skill levels of the country by taking knowledge, skill, aptitude and behaviors as the recipes for the success in a job. 1,00,000 candidates appeared for the test across 27 states, 7 union territories and more than 100 corporate players from the demand side of the Talent Supply chain. Only 33.95% were found employable, same can be interpreted that 2/3 of the skill pool is not fit to have a job. Mention must be made that the majority of the students are from Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Orissa, Karnataka, Delhi and Punjab”.

The Central Government is increasingly expecting the Tamil Nadu to play in the higher education sector for the international collaboration due to the relatively mature enrolment ratios and high intent to improve the quality of education, British Council Report (2015). The skills required for the students, technically termed as the ‘employability skills’ which is the need of the hour, is a highly difficult task to highlight with the particular skill set because a organization which considers a skill as the soft skill could be termed as the hard skill for another concern, but one could draw the general demarcation line between the basic skills and other skills. The students that belong to the Arts and Science colleges are expected to put on the basic skills in a prioritized manner for gaining the confidence at the time of attending the interview and subsequently securing a job.

Challenges in Imparting Employability Skills

‘Employability skills’ are those skills essential for receiving, keeping and being successful in a job. These are the basic skills necessary for acquiring, sustaining and pursuing the goals. The skills and attitudes that enable employees to get along with their colleagues, to make critical decisions, solve problems, develop respect and ultimately become strong ambassadors for the organization. As per the Allen Consulting Group report (2006), “employability skills are known by several other names, including key skills, core skills, life skills, essential skills, key competencies, necessary skills, and transferable skills. However industry’s preferred term is employability skills”.

“The skill deficit or skill gap is to be prioritized, the stakeholders working with young people need to have a clear sense of what they want to achieve and how they are going to attain their goal. As the new jobs are being generated, the number of suitable graduates available to grab these opportunities is not adequate. Government of India has adopted skill development as national priority over the next ten years.

The Government favours the formation of Skill Development mission both at the State and National levels”, India Skills Report (2015).

Conclusion

Employability skills are the attitudes that enable employees to get along with their colleagues, to make critical decisions, solve problems, develop respect and ultimately become strong ambassadors for the organisation – the least understanding of this would bring the most adverse affect in the life of the youth. Youth who want to prevent their vitality turned into a drought of summer, must have the flexibility, adaptability and yielding nature to preserve the moisture from being dried up by the

environmental forces. Employability skill is the yardstick for the quality of education. The number of graduates crowned by a university is not the indication of the quality of education, and then the number of crowns and gowns on the convocation day will be the number of enrollment in the job market.

References

1. Kevin Lowden, Stuart Hall, Dr Dely Elliot and Jon Lewin (2011) - Employers' perceptions of the employability skills of new graduates, Edge/SCRE Centre, p.vii.
2. Richard Bolden and Georgy Petrov (2008) - The Employer Engagement with Higher Education Literature Review, Centre for Leadership Studies University of Exeter November 2008, Compiled for the South West Higher Level Skills Project on behalf of HERDA South West. p.6.
3. United Kingdom Commission on Employability skills UKCES (2009) - The Employability challenge, Executive summary. p.1.
4. India Skill Report (2015) - Wheel Box Employability Skill Test p.14 & 16.
5. India Skill Report (2014) - Wheel Box Employability Skill Test p.7.
6. Allen Consulting Group a Report (2006) - Assessment and reporting of employability skills in training packages, A report to the Department of Education, Science and Training, Melbourne, March. p.11.
7. Employability Skills From Framework to Practice (2006): An Introductory Guide for Trainers and Assessors. p.52.